

Rural Entrepreneurship Strategies for Enhancing Community Development in Emohua Local Government Area Rivers State.

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Abstract

The study examined entrepreneurship education as a strategy for community development in Emohua local Government Area of Rivers State. Three specific objectives, three research questions and corresponding hypotheses guided the study. The study adopted a descriptive survey research design. The study was carried out in Emohua local government area of Rivers State. The population of the study was all community development committee members in the 8 communities in Emohua Local Government Area, Rivers State. The sample size of the study was 40 CDC members and 32 literate youth executives in Emohua Local Government Area Rivers State. The sample selection was done using cluster random sampling and purposively sampling technique respectively. The instrument used for the study was a self-designed questionnaire titled "Rural Entrepreneurship Strategies for Community Development". The design of the instrument was in form of a four-point rating scale of Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D) and Strongly Disagree (SD). The content of the instrument consists of value addition strategies, vocational skill acquisition strategies and agricultural entrepreneurship strategies for enhancing community development. The instrument was face and content validated by experts in community development. To ascertain the reliability of the instrument, Cronbach Alpha was used which gave 0.88, 0.75, and 0.91 reliability coefficient. The method of data analysis was mean and standard deviation. That is, any item with mean less than 2.50 were termed "disagree" while items greater than or equal to 2.50 were termed "agreed". To test the posed null hypotheses, z-test was used. The null hypotheses were accepted when the p-value is less than the level of significance (0.05), otherwise reject. The study found that value addition, vocational skill acquisition and agricultural entrepreneurship are rural entrepreneurship strategies for enhancing community development in in Emohua Local Government Area Rivers State. The study recommended that government should equip rural dwellers with value addition skills so as to improve the economic livelihood in the rural area. This will help to increase income generation among rural household.

Keywords: Rural Entrepreneurship, Strategies, Enhancing, Community Development

INTRODUCTION

Community development is a significant concept that aims at enhancing a sustainable socio-economic development with efforts of the people as the fulcrum. Ebere (2023) described community development as an educational method by which the efforts of the people themselves are united with those of government authorities to improve the economic, social and cultural condition of communities, to integrate these communities into the life of the nation and to enable them to contribute fully to national progress. Community development as defined by Cavaye (2004) is a holistic approach whereby local people can not only create more jobs, income and infrastructure, but also help their community become fundamentally better able to manage change. Community economic development is all about identifying and harnessing local community resources and opportunities and stimulating sustainable economic

and employment activity. (Kenyon, 1994). Hence, community development could be seen as a totality of communal activities that are stirred towards improving the economic, human, physical and infrastructural resources of a local environment.

Community development plays a crucial role in rural areas, as it helps to address the specific needs and aspirations of the local population. By empowering community members to actively participate in decision-making processes and take ownership of their own development, rural areas can experience positive change and growth (Ebere, 2023). Moreover, community development initiatives foster a sense of pride and belonging among residents, promoting social cohesion and a shared vision for the future. This sense of community can be a powerful force in overcoming

challenges and driving sustainable development in rural areas.

The primary aim of rural community development revolves around building the five capitals of a community – physical, financial, human, social and environmental (Cavaye, 2004). It is through participation in their community that people rethink problems and expand contacts and networks; building social capital. They learn new skills, build human capital, develop new economic options, build physical and financial capital and improve their environment. During the colonia era community development was the attention given to rural communities to further allow the exploitation of the agricultural and mineral resources that are abundant in the rural area rather than improving the quality of life of the rural people (Akpan, 2022). That shows that community development is beyond the exploitation of resources but the utilization of those resources for the betterment of the people in the community. This is why there is an advocate for rural entrepreneurship so as to equip rural dwellers with the ability to identify opportunities in their local environment.

Entrepreneurship development is increasingly seen as a promising alternative to traditional economic development, as it unlocks the potential of local citizens to create jobs and serve local tastes and markets (Fortunato, 2014). Rural entrepreneurship is seen as all forms of entrepreneurship that take place in areas characterized by large open spaces and small population settlements relative to the national context (Kalantaridis & Bika, 2006). The definition only focused on the spatial dimension of entrepreneurship activities characterized by small population settlement. However, Korsgaard, Müller and Tanvig (2015), stated that finer details of rural entrepreneurial activities should include profit-oriented and short-sighted opportunistic behaviour. Rural entrepreneurship involves new combinations of place-based or localized rural resources that create value not solely for the entrepreneur but also for the rural place (Muller & Korsgaard, 2014). Rural entrepreneurship draws on the innate (natural, cultural, historical, human, social and/or financial) resources of a place which the venture needs to support its development (Korsgaard, et al., 2015).

The concept of entrepreneurship is distinct on the recombination of available resources to create value with

the view of profit maximization and risk taking. In rural entrepreneurship, value or products and services are created or added (creatively) recombining resources from a given environment (Müller, 2013). The general perspective of rural entrepreneurship always centres around agricultural products, farmers being the chief entrepreneur considering the environment. However, this type of entrepreneurship is also a function that can be undertaken by a number of different rural actors including, but by no means restricted to, farming and farmers (Korsgaard, et al., 2015)

Value addition is a crucial aspect of rural entrepreneurship that aids economic development in the rural area. Value addition is the process of changing or transforming a product from its original state to a more valuable state (Coltrain, Barton & Boland, 2000). Fleming (2005) posited that value-addition is simply the act of adding value to a product, whether you have grown the initial product or not. It involves taking any product from one level to the next explained that many raw commodities have intrinsic value in their original state. Value addition could therefore be described as refers to the process of enhancing the economic, social, and cultural value of local resources and products. By adding value to these resources, communities can create new opportunities for economic growth and development. For example, field corn grown, harvested, and stored on a farm and then fed to livestock on that farm has value. In fact, value usually is added by feeding it to an animal, which transforms the corn into animal protein or meat. The value of a changed product is added value, such as processing wheat into flour. Value-addition has a particular importance in that it offers a strategy for transforming an unprofitable enterprise into a profitable one. A coffee grower can even add more value by opening the farm to visitors who can tour the farm and learn about the whole process of growing, harvesting, pulping, drying, milling, grading, roasting, packaging and, ultimately, tasting coffee (Fleming, 2005). Several innovative processes have been developed to transform traditional crops into nonfood products. These value-adding innovative activities use the research and emphasis that has been placed on finding industrial, nonfood uses for common agricultural products. Examples of these ventures include producing ethanol from corn, biodiesel from soybeans, and particleboard from straw (Coltrain, et al., 2000). While farmers by definition are not entrepreneurs, certain ways of running

and developing farms may well be highly entrepreneurial. Innovative ways of optimizing farming production are surely entrepreneurial; the same goes for farmers that add new business areas to their farming activities (Kitchen & Marsden, 2009). Beyond farming, there are diverse local resources in the rural areas that could be transformed into a more valuable product and centre for commercial attraction such as gardens, forests, lakes, rivers and other mineral resources. By so doing, economic activities in the rural area would be on the rising and this implies increase in economic turnout of rural household.

Vocational skill acquisition plays a crucial role in the development of rural communities through entrepreneurship. Vocational skill acquisition involves practical skills that enables an individual master a trade or job. Research has shown a significant relationship between vocational education and rural community development, highlighting the positive impact of vocational skill acquisition on the economic growth and prosperity of rural areas (Uduji & Okolo-Obasi, 2021). This could have motivated the launching of apprenticeship scheme by the federal government in a bid to fight unemployment and provide individuals with psychomotor skills (Inyang & Agwadu, 2017).

Furthermore, the empowerment of rural young people in informal farm entrepreneurship through vocational skill acquisition has been identified as a key factor in sustaining traditional livelihoods in Nigeria's oil-producing communities (Uduji & Okolo-Obasi, 2021). The development of vocational skills and entrepreneurship competencies in rural areas is also intertwined with the concept of community well-being and economic growth. Woodroffe et al. (2017) emphasized the need to encourage vocational skill acquisition among rural youths as it is instrumental to their self-sustenance. The preparation of rural and regional youths for the future world of work through authentic career-focused curriculum development has been highlighted as a means of leveraging rural communities and resources to develop innovative place-based career and curriculum learning, emphasizing the role of vocational skill acquisition in preparing individuals for the workforce and contributing to community development (Woodroffe et al., 2017). Acquisition of relevant skills and competence is a panacea in the fight against economic hardships and

unemployment in Nigeria as this will curtail crime rates through effective engagement of the youth in meaningful economic activities. This is to say that possession of relevant skills in an antidote to social problems (Emeka, Ezenwanne & Ezekwem, 2022). Vocational skill acquisition and entrepreneurship play a pivotal role in community development, particularly in rural areas. Equipping individuals with vocational and entrepreneurship skills not only fosters economic growth and prosperity but also contributes to the sustainability of traditional livelihoods, tourism development, and overall community well-being. When individuals in rural areas have access to vocational training and are equipped with the necessary skills, they can play an active role in addressing local challenges and driving economic growth (Senou & Manda, 2022). Additionally, vocational skill acquisition can create opportunities for entrepreneurship and self-employment, reducing dependence on traditional sectors such as agriculture. By diversifying the local economy, rural areas can become more resilient to external shocks and create a sustainable future for their residents (Sharif & Lonik, 2014).

Agricultural entrepreneurship is a major strategy to fostering community development particularly in the rural areas. Agricultural entrepreneurship involves the process of operating a farm and its related activities as a viable business venture (Amadi & Raji, 2021). Rural areas are areas where agricultural activities tend to be common, but agricultural entrepreneurship appears to be rare. All farmers produce but may not necessarily be involved in agricultural business. Involvement in agricultural business entails profit maximization, risk taking and opportunity oriented. The formulation of strategies that can be carried out in the development of young agricultural entrepreneurs is by implementing an aggressive strategy, namely taking advantage of very favorable situations, where young agricultural entrepreneurs have sufficient strength and opportunities, with the strength they have can take advantage of existing opportunities to expand and develop businesses so that entrepreneurial development young agriculture can be achieved and farmer regeneration and agricultural sector problems can be resolved. The aggressive strategies used were: 1) increasing the ease of access to capital assistance and financial stimuli by involving the banking sector; 2) creating several agro-tourism areas; 3) increasing the ease of access to information on business opportunities and business promotion; and 4) improving facilities for promotion events and entrepreneurial

achievement awards. (Refiswal, Julianti, & Supriana 2021)

Statement of the Problem

Rural areas are commonly attributed to poverty and low standard of living. This is true of many rural areas in Rivers State whereby majority of rural dwellers falls below the poverty line. In rural communities lies varieties of local resources that could be tapped for wealth creation among rural dwellers thereby leading to community development. For instance, some rural areas in rivers state has gardens, lakes, streams, rivers, precious stones, crops, plants that could be used to drive commercial activities. These natural resources remain under-utilized for community development purposes due to unavailability of skilled manpower for value addition, lack of vocational skill acquisition and lack of agricultural entrepreneurship mindset in rural area. This is because there seems to be low level of awareness on the strategies to adopt by community leaders to activate entrepreneurship mindset among rural dwellers. This low level of awareness could have been responsible for misappropriation of opportunities that lie in the natural environment of the rural areas. These issues made the researcher to embark on identifying rural entrepreneurship strategies for community development in Emohua Local Government Area Rivers State

Purpose of the study

The major purpose of the study was to examine rural entrepreneurship strategies for enhancing community development in Emohua local Government Area of Rivers State. In specific terms, the study sought to;

1. determine the value addition strategies for enhancing community development in Emohua Local Government Area of Rivers State.
2. determine vocational skill acquisition strategies for enhancing community development in Emohua Local Government Area of Rivers State
3. agricultural entrepreneurship strategies for enhancing community development in Emohua Local Government Area of Rivers State

Research Questions

The following research questions were posed for the study;

1. What are the value addition strategies for enhancing community development in Emohua Local Government Area of Rivers State?
2. What are the vocational skill acquisition strategies for enhancing community development in Emohua Local Government Area of Rivers State?
3. What are the agricultural entrepreneurship strategies for enhancing community development in Emohua Local Government Area of Rivers State?

Hypotheses

The hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance

1. There is no significant difference between the mean responses of CDC members and youth leaders on value addition strategies for enhancing community development in Emohua Local Government Area of Rivers State?
2. There is no significant difference between the mean responses of CDC members and youth leaders on vocational skill acquisition strategies for enhancing community development in Emohua Local Government Area of Rivers State?
3. There is no significant difference between the mean responses of CDC members and youth leaders on agricultural entrepreneurship strategies for enhancing community development in Emohua Local Government Area of Rivers State

METHODOLOGY

The adopted a descriptive survey research design. A descriptive survey research design is necessary in this study because it focused on describing a situation as it is, without manipulating the independent variable. The study would gather the opinion of the population in the area of study to appropriately describe the subject matter. Amadi (2020) posited that descriptive survey ultimately involves the responses of a particular set of people or entities representing a population on issues the researcher think it relates to them. The study was carried out in Emohua Local Government Area of Rivers State. Emohua Local Government Area is one of the 23 local government areas in Rivers State. Emohua is categorized as a rural area in Rivers State where majority of the

livelihood activities entails agriculture and rural resources. Emohua belongs to the Coastal Sand ridges zone of Rivers state. The area is drained by two major rivers, the New Calabar River and the Sombreiro River which extends towards the southern flank of Ndele community and Abua/Odua local Government area, where there exists a confluence (Ikezam & Kika, 2022). The drainage network pattern in the area does not fit into the conventional dendritic or trellised pattern of drainage. The area experiences poor drainage, this is because of its low-lying state and the abundance of surface water accompanied by excessive rainfall of about 2476mm. The soils in Emohua are made up of sandy-barns, humus, alluvium and the outer belt of salt water swamps, clay and mud. Hence, the chosen area is suitable for the study

The population of the study was all community development committee members in the 8 communities in Emohua Local Government Area, Rivers State. Although, as at the time of the study, there was no official record of the total number of community development members in Emohua Local Government Area, Rivers State. Cluster random sampling was used to select 5 community development committee (CDC) members from each of the 8 communities in Emohua Local Government Area, Rivers State. Also, 3 literate youth executives were purposively sampled from the 8

communities in Emohua, Rivers State. Hence, the sample size of the study was 40 CDC members and 32 literate youth executives in Emohua Local Government Area Rivers State. The instrument used for the study was a self-designed questionnaire titled “Rural Entrepreneurship Strategies for Community Development”. The design of the instrument was in form of a four point rating scale of Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D) and Strongly Disagree (SD). The content of the instrument consists of value addition strategies, vocational skill acquisition strategies and agricultural entrepreneurship strategies for enhancing community development. The instrument was face and content validated by experts in community development. To ascertain the reliability of the instrument, Cronbach Alpha was used which gave 0.88, 0.75, and 0.91 reliability coefficient. The method of data analysis was mean and standard deviation. That is, any item with mean less than 2.50 were termed “disagree” while items greater than or equal to 2.50 were termed “agreed”. To test the posed null hypotheses, z-test was used. The null hypotheses were accepted when the p-value is less than the level of significance (0.05), otherwise reject.

Result

Research Question 1: What are the value addition strategies for enhancing community development in Emohua Local Government Area of Rivers State?

Table 1: Value Addition Strategies for Enhancing Community Development in Emohua Local Government Area of Rivers State

S/N	Item	CDC Members= 40			Youths Leaders=32		
		Mean	S.D	Rmk	Mean	S.D	Rmk
1	Using agricultural farms for tourist visitors could enhance development of the community	3.48	0.62	Agree	3.13	0.64	Agree
2	Beautifying rural forest, gardens, rivers and lakes as a centre for tourist attraction can add value to communities for development	3.77	0.53	Agree	3.28	0.81	Agree
3	Training farmers on packaging and distribution of agricultural products can improve rural economic livelihood	3.29	1.02	Agree	3.23	0.75	Agree
4	Increasing the collaboration between industries and rural producers would facilitate industrial development in the rural area	3.01	1.00	Agree	3.44	0.74	Agree
5	Encouraging close ties between university researchers and rural producers/manufacturers can enhance economic innovation	3.22	0.79	Agree	3.21	0.83	Agree

6	Discovering the niche and consumer desires that could be serviced by locally available resources can aid community development	3.13	0.63	Agree	2.98	0.93	Agree
7	Transformation or processing of traditional crops into nonfood end uses like producing ethanol from corn, biodiesel from soybeans could improve community economic value	3.28	0.84	Agree	3.34	0.71	Agree
8	Encouraging industrial innovation on agricultural resources that are locally available can facilitate community development activities	3.49	0.64	Agree	3.21	0.64	Agree
9	Creating easy access to exportation of value-added products produced in the rural areas would increase income for rural household.	3.51	0.51	Agree	3.45	0.62	Agree
Grand Mean & S.D		3.35	0.73		3.25	0.74	

Field Survey, 2023

Table 1 presents the mean and standard deviation of responses of the respondents on the value addition strategies for enhancing community development in Emohua Local Government Area of Rivers State. The set criterion mean 2.50, shows that the respondents agreed that using agricultural farms for tourist visitors could enhance development of the community, beautifying rural forest, gardens, rivers and lakes as a centre for tourist attraction can add value to communities for development, training farmers on packaging and distribution of agricultural products can improve rural economic livelihood, increasing the collaboration between industries and rural producers would facilitate industrial development in the rural area, encouraging close ties between university researchers and rural producers/manufacturers can enhance economic innovation, discovering the niche and consumer desires that could be serviced by locally available resources can aid community development, transformation or processing of traditional crops into nonfood end uses like producing ethanol from corn, biodiesel from soybeans could improve community economic value, encouraging industrial innovation on agricultural resources that are locally available can facilitate community development

activities, and creating easy access to exportation of value-added products produced in the rural areas would increase income for rural household. The items have mean response greater than the benchmark mean (2.50) which shows that the respondents agreed to the item statements. The standard deviation showed the extent the responses were closed or widely dispersed. This finding is consistent with Muller (2013) who noted that in rural entrepreneurship, value or products and services are created or added (creatively) recombining resources from a given environment which then leads to economic improvement of that environment. Similarly, Korgaard et. al. (2015) holds that when values are added to rural resources it could generate notable income for rural economy thereby leading to community development. Kitchen and Marsden, (2009) still supports that view that when rural people are exposed to innovative ways of optimizing farming production rural entrepreneurs could surge from that awareness.

Research Question 2: What are the vocational skill acquisition strategies for enhancing community development in Emohua Local Government Area of Rivers State?

Table 2: Vocational Skill Acquisition Strategies for Enhancing Community Development in Emohua Local Government Area of Rivers State

S/N	Item	CDC Members= 40			Youths Leaders=32		
		Mean	S.D	Rmk	Mean	S.D	Rmk
1	Providing vocational skills acquisition graduates grants for them to be self-reliant would empower rural dwellers financially	3.31	0.69	Agree	3.56	0.61	Agree
2	Equipping rural youths with modern methods of practicing common skills can welcome technological advancements in the rural areas	3.34	0.67	Agree	3.54	0.74	Agree
3	Providing modern technologies used for skill acquisition and training would facilitate rural youth transformation	3.22	1.08	Agree	3.65	0.79	Agree
4	Creating enabling environment for vocational skill practices in rural communities could motivate the youths to acquire new skills for economic sustainability	3.19	1.04	Agree	3.49	0.83	Agree
5	Encouraging apprenticeship programmes for vocational skills acquisition among rural youths would boost youth passion for self-reliance	3.34	0.60	Agree	3.41	0.80	Agree
6	Sponsoring youths in internship programmes in neighbouring industries to acquire sustainable skills for community development	3.53	0.59	Agree	3.08	1.03	Agree
7	Providing opportunities for skill acquisition through skill acquisition training programmes in the rural areas	3.40	0.72	Agree	3.44	0.69	Agree
8	Creating access for vocation skill trainers to function and develop people rural communities	3.43	0.83	Agree	3.27	0.66	Agree
9	Building vocational centres for skill acquisition in the rural areas could contribute to community development	3.29	0.55	Agree	3.43	0.59	Agree
10	Provision of needed resources for vocational skill trainees for successful acquisition process would aid development human resource for community development	3.23	0.60	Agree	3.36	0.77	Agree
Grand Mean & S.D		3.33	0.74		3.42	0.75	

Field Survey, 2023

Table 2 shows the mean responses of the respondents on the vocational skill acquisition strategies for enhancing community development in Emohua Local Government Area of Rivers State. The benchmark mean of 2.50, showed that majority of the respondents agreed to the item statements posed in table 2. That is, providing vocational skills acquisition graduates grants for them to be self-reliant would empower rural dwellers financially, equipping rural youths with modern methods of practicing common skills can welcome technological advancements in the rural areas, providing modern technologies used for skill acquisition and training would facilitate rural youth transformation, creating enabling environment for vocational skill practices in

rural communities could motivate the youths to acquire new skills for economic sustainability, encouraging apprenticeship programmes for vocational skills acquisition among rural youths would boost youth passion for self-reliance, sponsoring youths in internship programmes in neighbouring industries to acquire sustainable skills for community development, providing opportunities for skill acquisition through skill acquisition training programmes in the rural areas, creating access for vocation skill trainers to function and develop people rural communities, building vocational centres for skill acquisition in the rural areas could contribute to community development, and provision of needed resources for vocational skill trainees for

successful acquisition process would aid development human resource for community development. The finding aligns with Emeka et al. (2022) who posited that possession of relevant vocational skill is an antidote to community economic crisis. Also Ud empowerment of rural young people in informal farm entrepreneurship through vocational skill acquisition has been identified

as a key factor in sustaining traditional livelihoods in Nigeria's oil-producing communities (Uduji & Okolo-Obasi, 2021).

Research Question 3: What are the agricultural entrepreneurship strategies for enhancing community development in Emohua Local Government Area of Rivers State?

Table 3: Mean Responses on Agricultural Entrepreneurship Strategies for Enhancing Community Development in Emohua Local Government Area of Rivers State

S/N	Item	CDC Members= 40			Youths Leaders=32		
		Mean	S.D	Remark	Mean	S.D	Remark
1	Taking advantage of favourable situation for expanding agricultural produce in rural area would aid economic development in rural area	3.40	0.59	Agree	3.23	0.72	Agree
2	Increasing farmers' ease of access to information on agricultural business opportunities and promotion would boost community development activities	3.58	0.77	Agree	3.23	0.64	Agree
3	Strengthening rural farmers' linkage with agro allied industries could increase the chances of industrial development in the rural areas	3.52	0.80	Agree	3.12	0.56	Agree
4	Encouraging farmers' diversification into cultivation of profitable agricultural raw materials would increase market chances in the rural areas	3.40	0.64	Agree	3.33	0.70	Agree
5	Developing inter-relationship links among farmers, financial institutions and consumers of agricultural products	3.69	0.69	Agree	3.46	0.67	Agree
6	Creating enabling environment for agricultural production and marketing would aid economic activities	3.59	0.52	Agree	3.54	1.03	Agree
7	creating several agro-tourism areas could boost community development	3.34	0.65	Agree	3.35	0.69	Agree
8	increasing the ease of access to capital assistance and financial stimuli by involving the banking sector would help community development	3.67	0.69	Agree	3.23	0.55	Agree
9	Providing good rural roads for easy transportation of agricultural produce facilitates community development	3.45	0.59	Agree	3.48	0.50	Agree
10	Sensitization of rural people on the opportunities available in agricultural production could aid development human resources in the community	3.67	0.73	Agree	3.05	0.57	Agree
Grand Mean & S.D		3.53	0.67		3.30	0.66	

Field Survey, 2023

Table 3 presents the mean responses of the respondents on the agricultural entrepreneurship strategies for enhancing community development in Emohua Local Government Area of Rivers State. Since the mean responses shown in table 3 is greater than the criterion mean value (2.50), this indicates that majority of the respondents agreed to the item statements. Specifically, the respondents agreed that taking advantage of favourable situation for expanding agricultural produce in rural area would aid economic development in rural area, increasing farmers' ease of access to information on agricultural business opportunities and promotion would boost community development activities, strengthening rural farmers' linkage with agro allied industries could increase the chances of industrial development in the rural areas, encouraging farmers' diversification into cultivation of profitable agricultural raw materials would increase market chances in the rural areas, developing inter-relationship links among farmers, financial institutions and consumers of agricultural products,

creating enabling environment for agricultural production and marketing would aid economic activities, creating several agro-tourism areas could boost community development, increasing the ease of access to capital assistance and financial stimuli by involving the banking sector would help community development, providing good rural roads for easy transportation of agricultural produce facilitates community development, and sensitization of rural people on the opportunities available in agricultural production could aid development human resources in the community

Hypotheses

There is no significant difference between the mean responses of CDC members and youth leaders on value addition strategies for enhancing community development in Emohua Local Government Area of Rivers State

Table 4: z-test Analysis on Value Addition Strategies for Enhancing Community Development in Rivers State

Respondents	N	Mean	S.D.	LOS	z-cal	z-crit	p-value	Rmk
CDC members	40	3.35	0.73	0.05	0.24	1.99	0.085	Accept
Youth Leaders	32	3.25	0.74					

Research Output, 2023

Table 4 shows the z-test analysis on value addition strategies for sustainable community development in Rivers State. The z-calculated value obtained was 0.24 which is less than the z-crit value of 1.99. Therefore, the hypothesis was upheld. This implied that there is no significant difference in the mean responses of CDC members and youth leaders on value addition strategies for enhancing community development in Emohua Local Government Area of Rivers State

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant difference between the mean responses of CDC members and youth leaders on vocational skill acquisition strategies for enhancing community development in Emohua Local Government Area of Rivers State?

Table 5: z-test Analysis on Vocational Skill Acquisition Strategies for Enhancing Community Development in Rivers State

Respondents	N	Mean	S.D.	LOS	z-cal	z-crit	p-value	Rmk
CDC members	40	3.33	0.74	0.05	0.29	1.99	0.08	Accept
Youth Leaders	32	3.42	0.75					

Research Output, 2023

Table 5 shows the z-test analysis on value addition strategies for sustainable community development in Rivers State. The z-calculated value obtained was 0.24 which is less than the z-crit value of 1.99. Therefore, the null hypothesis was failed to reject.

There is no significant difference between the mean responses of CDC members and youth leaders on agricultural entrepreneurship strategies for enhancing community development in Emohua Local Government Area of Rivers State

Table 6: z-test Analysis on Agricultural Entrepreneurship Strategies for Enhancing Community Development in Rivers State

Respondents	N	Mean	S.D.	LOS	z-cal	z-crit	p-value	Rmk
CDC members	40	3.53	0.67	0.05	0.51	1.99	0.092	Accept
Youth Leaders	32	3.30	0.66					

Research Output, 2023

Table 6 shows the z-test analysis on agricultural entrepreneurship strategies for sustainable community development in Rivers State. The z-calculated value obtained was 0.24 which is less than the z-crit value of 1.99. Therefore, the hypothesis was upheld. This implied that there is no significant difference in the mean responses of CDC members and youth leaders on agricultural entrepreneurship strategies for enhancing community development in Emohua Local Government Area of Rivers State

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings of the study, it was concluded that rural entrepreneurship is a vital means of aiding community development particularly in the aspect economic empowerment. The rural entrepreneurship strategies identified in this study were value addition strategies, vocational skill acquisition strategies and agricultural entrepreneurship strategies. In value addition, improving the state of local resources available in the rural areas aids community development while vocational skill acquisition is focused on equipping and developing the human resources in the rural areas with needed skill for self-sustainability, which is a notable aspect of community development. In agricultural entrepreneurship the taking advantage of favourable situation for expanding agricultural produce, strengthening rural farmers' linkage with agro allied industries amongst others can aid development of rural communities.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of the study, it was recommended that

1. Government should equip rural dwellers with value addition skills so as to improve the economic livelihood in the rural area. This will help to increase income generation among rural household
2. Community leaders should encourage acquisition of vocational skills among youths by providing needed resources for vocational skill acquisition such as centres for skill acquisition, tools and skill trainers. This would create appropriate environment for vocational skill acquisition among rural youths
3. Government should encourage farmers by strengthening the market links between agro-allied industries and rural farmers. By so doing, farmers would be motivated into commercial scale of production to boost their household income.

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